

CORRECTION OF ATTENTION IN PRIMARY CLASSES AND PREVENTION OF LACK OF ASSIMILATION

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Abstract. *This article focuses on scientific psychological and pedagogical reflections on the tasks of correcting attention and preventing assimilation in the elementary grades.*

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The factors that influence the assimilation of primary students are considered to be of great importance. In order for students to become perfect people in the future, their training and etiquette will require a lot of responsibility for our educators. Many of our scientists have expressed their opinion on the development of man as a perfect person.

We can cite as an example the work of a number of our scholars, including Abu Nasr Farabi, Ibn Sina, Yusuf Hos Khojib, from Eastern thinkers. For example, one of the main issues in Yusuf Khos Hajib's "Qutadg-U bilig" is the upbringing of a perfect person. In his work, Adib outlines his principles on the basis of how he imagined the most perfect, a person capable of meeting the demands of society at that time: A. Jami's works "Bahoristan", "Tuhfatul ahror", "Silsilatuz Zahab" and others express ideas about Science, Education, Vocational Studies, good qualities and decency.

Today, it is required to educate mentally developed, talented young people who serve for the development and prosperity of our country. Therefore, without perfecting the educational process, it is impossible to form the youth demanded by society.

It is known that the periods of growth, development and formation of any person do not occur without educational activities. Mental development and education are closely related activities. Radical reform of the educational system is a requirement of the current period, changes in the educational system, the perfection of the curriculum, the organization of problem classes are aimed at perfecting education [3.b.77]. Activities that are carried out when the student is not active in the educational process do not give the desired result. In the educational process, it is also important to train students to work independently. In the process of education, they are familiar with the various requirements for schoolchildren. Psychologically prepared to master the sciences. They develop skills, competencies in order to gain knowledge in their psyche. The main activity of primary students is reading. Educational activities create new conditions for the development of speech, thinking, abilities from the child. Upon arrival at school, the child switches to a psychologically new system of relationships with those around him. He begins to feel a radical change in his life, new obligations to him, a boyish fading to the requirements of educational activities, going to school every day. The fact that family members are interested in the achievements of the child in educational activities, as well as in controlling him, the attitude towards him in a new form, which is being done, gives rise to a change in attitude towards himself to the full feeling that his social status Has Changed [5, P.197].

Attention to the child preparing for school education will be relatively long duration and conditionally stable. The features of the child's attention can be seen in role - playing and plot games, drawing and building-living activities, making toys from clay and plasticine, performing mathematical actions in a yeshiva, listening to and composing a story.

On the ground of responsible, multifaceted and complex activities of an elementary school teacher lie such important tasks as educating the younger generation as patriotic, polite, faith-loving, as well as arming them with scientific knowledge. And the implementation of these depends on the diverse activities of the teacher: the education of children, the ability to organize after-school and extracurricular activities, the transfer, the conduct of pedagogical propaganda among parents and the formation of a class community. All this requires the teacher to have deep knowledge, love his field, children.

On the way to the rise of our republic, which is moving towards development today, dedicated teachers will be needed who can be proud of the rich history, culture, traditions of our people and promote it in the youth circle of students. Obviously, such teachers are elementary school teachers.

One of the main tasks of an elementary school teacher is to educate the young generation, our future, in the right, humane spirit. Primary classes are the initial stage of school education, with children taking Step 1 in education under the guidance of a teacher.

For the first time, students acquire knowledge, skills and qualifications in educational activities. The teacher works alone with the class and often acts as a tutor. The attitude of teachers towards children is characterized by great kindness and care. The ability of students to maintain proper interactions with teachers and to re-educate students based on their growth and development is also important to the class leader. The School Charter defines the main tasks of the class leader. The head of the class is in a joint relationship with all-rounders and carries out educational work with his class. It achieves the unity of pedagogical requirements imposed by teachers on students. Parents, group caregivers with extended days, are in constant contact with the public. Organizes the provision of assistance to the student in the necessary vaqit. The class will carry the specified documents and submit it to the school administration. Teachers conduct work to strengthen their health and teach them to work. The peculiarity of the work of the class leader is that it forms not an ordinary children's team, but a team of students. The main task of students is to study.

Therefore, the class leader initially determines how the children react to their studies, how they behave, whether they diligently perform their homework or not. And finally the most important thing is to find out what their goals in their studies consist of. This takes into account whether or not the objects have an essence of social significance. In this regard, the teacher can face various situations at the initial stage of working with the class. The main goal of an elementary school teacher is to form literacy skills in the student, develop their worldview, ethics, aesthetic taste, abilities and beliefs, and prepare him to become a certain professional. The process of primary education is an extremely responsible, complex process. Therefore, operating in this process requires a huge amount of effort, perseverance, patience, creativity from the teacher. For the first time, the teacher holds a pencil in the hands of the student, teaches him the letter, reading, enriches his perception of tevarak-surroundings, and forms a stable class community. Also at this time, the teacher is required to be attentive to each student, to take into account their interests and character traits.

The child seeks to focus his attention on a specific object, to control his attention with a certain level of skill in the distribution of collection, and to accumulate it at the right time. Elementary students will be indulged in gullible external taasurots. As our great symptoms point out, the character of a person is composed more than anyone in the first years of his life, and the qualities that appear in it during this period are firmly established and become the second nature of a person. In the second nature of Man, the formation of natural feelings, qualities in order to form the norms of high morality, the whole responsibility falls on the responsibility of the elementary school teacher. During this period of the child, every sentence of the teacher, every act of show, acts as a standard of truth for him. Because students strongly trust teachers. They listen to his feedback. They are seriously affected by pedagogical femininity.

They assimilate the studied materials from memory without logical analysis, the reasons for which are that their mechanical memory develops more honestly than other types of memory, making it possible to remember information precisely without changes.

1) students do not realize the task set by the teacher, which results in what they see as a verbatim repetition of his request to “explain correctly”.

2) their lack of speech richness (ignorance of scientific terms and language laws), creative filling of material, the inability to add to it makes it easier to return word by word.

Readers do not know how to remember the text using the right methods. A.A Smirnov argues that, as an appropriate way to remember, it is possible to classify from meaningful words in the text into groups, find a base point, draw up a plan for words, and recommend repeating a new topic, perceiving the topics mentioned. Logical memory is improved in readers by remembering and recalling the essence of the text, various reflections, arguments, scientific foundations. In mental work, it is impossible to cultivate the ability to strive for knowledge, not creating independence. Therefore, it is important to teach Boas to read annotations, interpret the condition of the issue, create and solve problem situations. The productivity of voluntary recall and voluntary recall largely depends on the degree of mental activity of students. It has been proven in psychological diagnostic studies that first and second graders can only sit carefully for 30-35 minutes in the lesson, concentrate their attention on a specific object and hold it in it.

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